

TUTOR POSITION AND HISTORY**Gozzal Abdullaeva**

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Abstract. *This article discusses the position of tutor and its dictionary meaning, history of origin and current functions.*

Keywords: *tutor, position, practice, field, education, practical training.*

ДОЛЖНОСТЬ И ИСТОРИЯ РЕПЕТИТОРА

Аннотация. *В статье рассматривается должность репетитора и ее словарное значение, история происхождения и текущие функции.*

Ключевые слова: *репетитор, должность, практика, сфера, образование, практическая подготовка.*

The word "tutor" comes from the Latin "Tutorem" - teacher, mentor. In some cases, he acts as a liaison between the lecturer and the listener, that is, as a consultant and mentor in the broad acquisition of knowledge given by the lecturer. This word is not included in the explanatory dictionary of the Uzbek language. Despite this, it is used as a new term not only in our language, but also as a specific position in higher education. By the relevant government decision, from September 1, 2021, the institute of "group coach" in working with students was abolished, and the practice of assigning "Tutors" to provide close assistance in solving problems for 1st-3rd year students was established. In accordance with the document, the position of "Tutor" was introduced at the rate of 1 staff unit for every 120-150 students. The main task of the "Tutor" is to strengthen relations between the university and students in the effective organization of the educational and upbringing process, to help students adapt to university life and the educational process, to provide them with methodological, social and psychological support, and to increase students' love for their chosen profession. At the same time, they regularly analyze and improve the quality of the lessons of the boys and girls, ensure that they spend their free time meaningfully, and are constantly aware of their social situation.

So, does the word "Tutor" cause negativity in the language? Of course, it does. For example, a foreign word replaces an Uzbek word, the words "ustoz", "murabbiy" are rarely pronounced, and the scope of use of the word "Tutor" expands. As a result, this leads to the loss and devaluation of Uzbek words. Therefore, it would be appropriate to use words that are understandable to everyone, such as a teacher, a promoter of enlightenment, instead of "Tutor".

In essence, these words can be used instead of the term “Tutor”. If this word is to be used as a regular term in our language, it should first be included in the explanatory dictionary of the Uzbek language and used together with its synonyms.

In the current globalization environment, the foundation of all spheres is education. Because it is from educational institutions that mature specialists who are needed by society and who manage it are being trained. In this regard, the education of young personnel who are in line with the requirements of the times, strong-willed, comprehensively thoughtful, and whose interests are focused on the idea of creativity is one of the urgent tasks facing educational institutions today.

The tutoring system is also aimed at these goals. It is an important form and tool for the systematic and effective implementation of the educational process in a higher educational institution. A tutor is a pedagogue who helps students in their personal development, worthy participation in competitions and olympiads at the educational institution, republican and international levels, as well as in spending their free time meaningfully. He is engaged in directing young people to a profession, educating them in the spirit of love for the Motherland, involving them in various scientific circles, studying their problems and shortcomings and finding comprehensive solutions to them.

Like any innovation, this direction also has a history of origin. Many sources indicate that the first tutors appeared in the 12th century at the universities of Oxford and Cambridge in England. The term is borrowed from the English language and means “home tutor, teacher, mentor, guardian.” The word “tutoring” means supporting a person’s personal education. This is a very delicate, “private” work activity. According to the Russian researcher N.V. Rybalkina, by the end of the 16th century, the tutor becomes an important person responsible for the education of his subordinate students in the university education system. In the 17th century, the scope of the tutor’s activities expanded further, and now he is also entrusted with teaching duties. He determines which practical classes and lectures the student should attend, monitors whether the students are studying well and are ready for exams. From the 17th century onwards, the tutoring system began to be officially recognized as an integral part of the English higher education system.

According to current data, 90% of tutors in modern Oxford and 75% in Cambridge work with 1 or 2 students. Although they do not have special education, they are responsible for guiding students both during their studies and during their holidays, providing spiritual guidance. More precisely, the main form of tutor work is to work with a student individually and in a team or to be an educational consultant for him.

A number of general requirements are imposed on the tutor, such as leadership, organization, initiative, aspiration, oratory skills, communication skills, skills in working with modern information and communication and innovative pedagogical technologies, and knowledge of regulatory and legal documents related to the educational process.

As is known, since students are admitted to the first stage or come through the transfer of their studies, a database related to them is not formed. Each tutor sits individually with the students in the academic group assigned to him, asks for all the information from the student's name to his address, interests, close relatives, and in general, fills the specified database according to the scale and summary form provided by the university or dean's office. It is important to further increase the tutor's responsibility in this work. Because the accuracy, correctness, and absence of errors in the formalization of the information provided by the student require increased attention. Sometimes we witness that students, especially in the first stage and even in senior courses, are not aware of the conditions of the university. At such times, he needs a person to guide him. It is necessary to familiarize students with student dormitories, information resource centers, various clubs, sports complexes, university museums, culture and music halls, etc., aimed at meaningfully organizing students' free time. It is necessary to ensure that young people become familiar with the necessary buildings and conditions within the scope of their interests in the first ten days. This will further expand their ability to organize and continue their studies and research from the very first days. It is also important to take into account the interests of students in universities. Today's modern system tutors are performing innovative, motivational, effective organizational and practical work in the purposeful organization of students' free time, using the mechanism of hours and minutes, rather than time.

Of course, the correct orientation of each student, the effective and productive organization of their free time will serve to produce more educated, capable personnel for society. As is known, our state and higher educational institutions are introducing prestigious scholarships and grants.

These include prestigious scholarships named after the President, Navoi, Beruni, Ibn Sina, Islam Karimov (and others). There is also an opportunity to participate in international or republican grants and projects and become a winner. For this, it is necessary to correctly direct the student and work with him systematically. These tasks also fall on the tutor. Many researchers and experts emphasize that supporting tutoring is one of the most effective forms of developing a unique mentoring in the system of continuing education. Currently, tutoring is also recognized as one of the innovative pedagogical activities implemented by advanced educators. Therefore, there are many factors that have led to the increased interest in tutoring in our country.

One of them is the need to use tutoring technologies in higher education institutions, and another is the fact that tutoring ideas have begun to be included in state educational programs.

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